

Exhibition Introduction

Seeing Wilde Songs

Poetry, music, and painting often blur together. In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, artists across Europe and North America began embracing this overlap, experimenting with ways to capture fleeting moments of sensation. Painters explored light and atmosphere, poets wrote in bursts of color and musical phrasing, and composers sought ways to give sound a visual or physical presence. This shared approach came to be known as Impressionism—a way of experiencing the world through shifting, overlapping senses.

Seeing Wilde Songs traces these crossings through the poetry of Oscar Wilde and the music of composer Charles T. Griffes. Griffes was drawn to Wilde's poems for their musical titles, rhythmic language, and vivid color imagery. In setting these works to music, Griffes reshaped Wilde's verse as sound, drawing out the sensory resonances already embedded in the poems.

For Griffes, this attraction to Wilde's sensory language was more than metaphor. He experienced synesthesia: a form of perception in which the senses cross. Certain musical notes appeared to him as specific colors. Wilde's luminous imagery—especially his repeated use of yellow and gold—thus became not only poetic description but a sensory catalyst, guiding Griffes' compositional choices and tonal color.

Throughout the gallery, each display brings together a poem, visual art, musical setting, and audio recording. As you move through the space, listen, look, and read for moments when sound seems to take on color, images suggest music, and poetry hovers between the senses.

Artist Biographies

Oscar Wilde

Oscar Wilde (1854–1900) was an Irish author associated with Aestheticism and the late nineteenth century's fascination with beauty, sensation, and artistic form. While best known for his plays and fiction, Wilde published a volume of poetry in 1881 which featured several "Impression" poems. These works often borrow the language of music—using titles such as "Symphony in Yellow" and describing scenes as harmonies, nocturnes, or as tonal studies in mood and color. Wilde relied heavily on yellow and gold imagery: a palette echoed in his writing and public aesthetic. His poetry imagines a convergence of sound, sight, and sensation.

Charles T. Griffes

Charles T. Griffes (1884–1920) was an American composer whose works helped shape early twentieth-century musical Impressionism in the United States. Born in New York and trained in Berlin, Griffes composed primarily for piano, chamber ensembles, and voice. He experienced absolute pitch and synesthesia, a form of perception in which sound and color are linked. Certain musical keys appeared to him as distinct colors—E-flat, for example, as yellow or gold. When Griffes encountered Wilde's poetry—rich with musical language and

luminous color—he sought to translate those impressions into sound. The resulting “Wilde songs,” as he described them, remain among his most celebrated works.

Object Labels

Symphony in Yellow

Wilde’s poem treats color as music, repeating “yellow” as a structuring refrain. When Griffes set the poem to music, he responded in kind—shaping sound around color and atmosphere. In the manuscript sketch of the song, tonal shifts mirror the fog, river, and light shared with these Impressionist paintings.

La Fuite de la Lune

Wilde turns moonlight into texture—silence pierced by distant sound, the moon “wrapped in yellow gauze.” Griffes’ composition translates that veiled light into music, suspending melody and harmony. Moonlit Impressionist paintings echo this shared fascination with obscured light and drifting atmosphere.

Le Jardin

Wilde’s garden is all texture and color—white lilies, crimson petals, dusty gold. The surrounding garden scenes echo this approach, where emotion and atmosphere linger longer than narrative certainty. Griffes’ composition leaves the final musical tones unresolved—opening *Four Impressions*, the collection he described as his “four Wilde songs.”

Impression du Matin

Inspired by views of London, Wilde frames morning as color becoming sound. Griffes translates this vision into music like the yellow fog that never fully settles, changing meter and harmony as the city wakes. Bells ring, birds stir, and the final human figure emerges apart—quiet, exposed, unforgettable.

La Mer

Mist, moonlight, and motion dominate Wilde’s sea. A tawny moon glares through the storm as the sea overwhelms all traces of the ship. Griffes’ music follows the storm’s arc from gathering power to spent force. Like the surrounding paintings, the scene resists resolution, leaving only light, waves, and lingering unease.

Le Réveillon

In *Le Réveillon*, dawn arrives in strokes of color rather than clear forms; it emerges through shifting reds, whites, and golds. Griffes heightens these contrasts through luminous tone and texture. A single word change in his composition—“flushed with gold”—reveals how musical necessity subtly refines dawn’s palette.

Les Ballons

Wilde first published “*Les Ballons*” as a hand-lettered poem within an illustrated spread. Its riot of color fascinated Griffes, who repeatedly revised without fully composing a sound palette that satisfied him. Though unfinished at his death, the work was later completed, preserving his exploration of sound, color, and motion.